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The European Law beyond the European Legal Order

Abstract

The paper addresses the effects of European law. The first, of paramount importance, is conducive towards the European legal order of the European Communities and of the European Union. Moreover, European law has simultaneously contributed to the development at supranational level of a teleological vision of governance; the values that are considered European per se; the human rights that are better protected; the identity in sensu lato, exceeding the cultural meaning; at global level to a source for international law and national law of third countries. The implications of these effects are examined to highlight the significance of the European law in the process of European integration and enhancing the European actorness in the global order; additionally, the unique design of European law may drive supranational and international stability or instability depending on players' interests.

Key words: European law, effects, European legal order, values, identity

Introduction

The history of European unification is old as Europe itself. For centuries politicians had been striving at uniting Europe by hard instruments. A change of paradigm for uniting Europe occurred in the nineteenth century, when political actors opted for benevolent, soft tools. Since then a lot of incentives have emerged by addressing this issue. The focus transcended the communication for uniting Europe from narrow political circles to masses of people by various means in which thinkers, philosophers and writers were involved.

The philosophy of small steps and legal binding agreements prevailed over all initiatives. The European Union – a successor of the European

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Community – represents a legal reality. This legal reality shaped and continues to shape the constitution of a united Europe, the European Union. Does the legal reality refer only to a new legal order of the Member States that form the European Union? Does the legal reality produce effects only inside the legal order, or outside too? What kind of effects are they? What do they influence after all? These cogent questions claim for reasoning answers which are rooted in European law.

Such an approach originates from the uniqueness of European law in the contemporary world, as it was with Roman law in ancient times. Without having the intention to compare these two systems of law, however, it is fair to say that European law exceeds by far through its magnitude, significance and stance for transformative regional and global changes. In order to clarify it, scrutinising answers to the above-mentioned questions are required by revealing the development of the European *acquis*, its internal and international effects, in what way and how it affected a world competitor, the European Union.

1. *Acquis communautaire*

The *Acquis communautaire* (*acquis*: that has been acquired or obtained; *communautaire*: of the community) – or community *acquis*, sometimes called the EU *acquis*, or often shortened to *acquis* – is a central legal concept of the European Union. The French term refers to the legal order of the European Union. The EU's *acquis* is the cumulative body of European Union law applicable in the European Union. *In sensu stricto*, the EU's *acquis* consists of primary, secondary and tertiary legislation. *In sensu lato* the European Union law comprises the rules of the EU legal order, including general principles of law, the case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union, law flowing from the EU's external relations, and supplementary law contained in conventions and similar agreements concluded between the European countries to give effect to Treaty provisions. So, the EU's *acquis* is fundamental, dynamic, constantly developing and evolving.

Thus, the EU's *acquis* is described as a body of common rights and obligations that are binding on all EU Member States. All EU Member States are bound to comply with the *acquis communautaire*, which denotes the primacy of EU law over national law of EU Member States. Applicant countries must accept the *acquis communautaire* and incorporate it into their own legal systems before they can join the European Union. Certain

derogations from the EU's *acquis* may be granted only in exceptional cases and are limited in scope *per se*. Applicant countries must adjust their state institutions and bring their national legislations in line with the EU's *acquis*. During the negotiations for enlargement the *acquis* varied in the number of chapters. For instance, in the last enlargement (Croatia) the *acquis* was split into thirty five chapters: free movement of goods; freedom of movement for workers; right of establishment and freedom to provide services; free movement of capital; public procurement; company law; intellectual property law; competition policy; financial services; information society and media; agriculture and rural development; food safety, veterinary and phytosanitary policy; fisheries; transport policy; energy; taxation; economic and monetary policy; statistics; social policy and employment (including anti-discrimination and equal opportunities for women and men); enterprise and industrial policy; trans-European networks; regional policy and co-ordination of structural instruments; judiciary and fundamental rights; justice, freedom and security; science and research; education and culture; environment; consumer and health protection; the customs union; external relations; foreign, security and defence policy; financial control; financial and budgetary provisions; institutions; and other issues.

The EU's *acquis* is crucial for understanding the constitution of the European Union, the enlargement procedure and the process of European integration. Moreover, the EU's *acquis* is critical for understanding the effects it produces inside and outside the EU legal order.

2. European Law: Community Effects

Legal effects of the European Union law refer to the multitude of legal effects that EU legal norms may generate in the EU legal order and in the national legal systems of the Member States. The rules for the national application of EU law include direct effects, indirect effects, and primacy of EU law (Bobek 2017, 143–176).

Legal effects are distinguished from political, economic, social, and psychological effects that EU law may have on individuals, communities and European society at large. However, the latter effects are not neglectable as they may have the same weight or may indicate more than legal effects, because taken altogether legal and non-legal effects may affect the human condition in the European community, even though only legal effects constitute an accepted legal basis for the conduct of the community.

Ultimately, legal and non-legal effects overlap to some extent, considering that legal norms regulate political and social areas. Positive or negative psychological effects may emerge by adequate or inadequate provision of ethical aspects into legal norms.

On the one hand, EU law contributed to the establishment of the European legal order. On the other hand, EU law also produced non-legal effects, i.e. political, economic, social and psychological effects at national and community levels.

Unification. Among political effects, the greatest realisation is a united Europe, i.e. the European Union, a supranational organisation of peoples and states that was built not by force, the hard tools used in the past, but by soft instruments excluding the use of military force.

The unification of Europe, a united Europe, has led to democratic and efficient instruments of governance at local, national and supranational levels, reconciling all players; a transparent decision-making process; balanced sharing of powers, etc.

Integration. Among economic and social effects, integration seems to be a never-ending process, as it has a temporal dimension. Integration represents the scope and the nature of the European Union. Integration has always been on track. The process of European integration is as lengthy as the European Union itself.

Convergence policy and attenuation of regional disparities (Meliciani 2016) are essentially linked to socio-economic factors of different Member States, Western and Eastern standards, industrial and agricultural regions, central and peripheral areas, newcomers, etc.

Creation of the unique/single European market, customs union, Schengen area, eurozone, and free movement (of goods, persons, capital, and services) contributed to the development and improvement of economic milieu inside the European Union to a greater market exempted from various taxes, the promotion of greater competition among various agents and more innovative economies.

The ensemble of unification and integration may be displayed by an axis in which unification is associated to space and integration to time. An imaginary curve would intersect spatial and temporal points that move obliquely upwards but not always in a straight-line graph.

Fig. 1. Unification-Integration Axis

Source: own elaboration, 2019.

Security and Safety. Security and safety are important pillars of the EU legal order. Security is a pre-requisite for stability and growth in the European Union. EU treaties and policies recognise them indispensable for wellbeing of the community. For that to happen, the European Union must play an active role in dealing with local, national, regional and supranational challenges. Some germs of existing challenges come from outside of the European Union. Thus, the European Union is engaged in such challenges as poverty, humanitarian disasters, conflict prevention and resolution. The European Union acts through concrete actions that support development, reduce the risk of disasters and conflicts in order to build resilient societies. In this way the European Union improves its capacities, preparedness and response to security and safety threats.

The European Union’s internal and external policies are aimed at supporting stability and security by enhancing the capabilities for prevention and response to the threats it faces alone or jointly with other actors at regional and/or global levels.

European Law: Driver of Values. For sure the values represent a crucial chapter in the constitution and the history of the European Union. These values are prescribed in the constitutional treaties. The European Union is “founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights” (CTEU, art. 2). These values became a common pool of values for the Member States and adhering countries. The European values have been building synergies between people and countries for almost seven decades of sharing them inside and outside the EU legal order.

In the debates over values, there are voices (e.g. Gideon Rachman) asserting that the European Union is not based on values, it is just an alliance. Such an assertion is quite questionable. As a proof of this stands the unity of the European Union in face of various crises (economic, financial, the story of Brexit, etc.). It is possible because the European values are socio-centric. If they were state-centric, just in such case any claim of an alliance would be valid. By extrapolation the European Union is an alliance, but an alliance of peoples first and foremost.

Thus, European law is a driver of values as such, oriented towards and granted to individuals that form the European Union. Considering the direct effects of European law in the national systems of law, the Member States do keep to these values.

European values are also exported to third countries' legal systems as well, through the agreements that the European Union concludes (e.g. ENP countries, etc.).

European Law: Driver of Identity. European law could be regarded as a driver of European identity as well. Both hard and soft effects of European law have left traces on the identity of the peoples living in the European Union. Here the concept of European identity refers to the European Union and not to the continent of Europe, taking into consideration that there is no full overlapping of these two categories. It is worth observing how European law contributed to formation of European identity. European identity formation is also an evolutionary process and its foundations lay in the founding treaties. There are scholars who ask if a European identity exists (Dittrich van Weringh 2005) or even propose the idea that a common European identity is “an illusion” (White 2012, 103–111).

It is fair to say that the meaning of identity – a complex, complicated and sometimes unclear concept – plays a central role in the European community. A valuable reference is that identity refers to “(a) a social category, defined by membership rules and (alleged) characteristic attributes or expected behaviours, or (b) socially distinguishing features that a person takes a special pride in or views as unchangeable but socially consequential (or (a) and (b) at once)” (Fearon 1999). In a broad sense the sameness of essential character can be revealed.

Strictly speaking from the legal point of view, the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht Treaty), signed in 1992, introduced an innovative legal category, that of European citizenship. The purpose was “to strengthen the protection of the rights and interests of the nationals of its Member States through the introduction of a citizenship of the Union” (TEU, art. B);

“Citizenship of the Union is hereby established. Every person holding the nationality of a Member State shall be a citizen of the Union. Citizens of the Union shall enjoy the rights conferred by this Treaty and shall be subject to the duties imposed thereby” (TEU, art. 8).

Simon Schunz considers that European identity is an “unfinished business” (Schunz 2012). In his pertinent policy review, he follows four main theoretical concepts driving the study of European identity: European identity and identification with Europe; Europeanisation; transnationalism and cosmopolitanism. Then he identifies nine dimensions for the expression of European identity: multiple social identities and biographical identity; transnational intimate relationships; collective action; standardisation and regulation; cultural production; intercultural translation; inclusion/exclusion; structural conditions and opportunity structures; the public sphere and state-regulated institutions (Schunz 2012).

European identity seems to be based on two models of formation: the structuralist model (deriving from association with other Europeans) and the culturalist model (deriving from core, European values and their expression, especially in governance and legal order) (Recchi 2012).

There are scholars who are in favour of active promotion of initiatives on European identity. Stefan Hojelid focuses on obstacles and possibilities (Hojelid 2001). In a recent study Mathias Dolls and Clemens Fuest analyse the existing policies and recommend concrete proposals on how to activate an “EU feeling”: how to encourage European identity (Dolls, Fuest 2018).

European identity must be treated in a broader sense of belonging to the same geography, history, culture and legal order. European identity resides in a feeling of exclusive belonging to the European Union. As an open process, the European identity is being shaped continuously.

3. European Law: International Effects

International treaties make part in the hierarchy of European legal order (CTFUE, art. 216). On one hand, in order to produce effects, they must fulfil three conditions: binding; clear, precise and unconditional provision capable of direct application; and unprecluded effect.

On the other hand, in the opposite way the contribution of European law to the development of international law is also certain: the European Union concludes international treaties; the European Union is a member of some international organisations; the European Union participates

actively in shaping of international law (cf. Smith 2010, 224–241; Kochenov, Amtenbrink 2013, 1–18; Wouters, Chané, Odermatt 2014). The European Union is an “actor of international law” (Lenaerts, de Smijter 1999, 95–138). There are voices considering European law as international law (Moorhead 2012, 125–144).

Additionally, European Union law has effects on the national law systems of third countries in the form of law approximation. It especially happens with the countries with which there are concluded partnership and cooperation agreements, and association agreements. In this respect, the European Union covers a large geographical area in supporting development, security and political dialogue with the countries in the Western Balkans, the Mediterranean, the Middle East, Eastern Europe, Central Asia and Latin America. Human rights and democracy are among the key elements in promoting cooperation for mutual benefits.

European Actorness. The abovementioned facts speak in favour of European actorness at international level. In other words, the European Union has the status of global actor in international relations due to its presence and contribution in such areas as law, diplomacy, economic affairs, culture, etc.

4. What Is in Crisis?

A lot of discussions and debates have emerged lately in the European Union about a specific crisis or certain crises, including research results provided by the academic world. What is not expressly mentioned in these debates is the area of competences. Crises occur in the areas of competences adjudicated by national authorities, not in those conferred to the European Union. Under the principle of conferral, the European Union acts only in the limits of its competences given by the Member States. Those competences that are not given to the European Union remain under the authority of the Member States. The division of competences between the European Union and its Member States falls into three categories:

- exclusive competences,
- shared competences,
- supporting competences.

Exclusive competences (CTFEU, art. 3) refer to areas in which the European Union alone can legislate and adopt binding acts. The Member States may do so only if empowered by the European Union. But as a rule, the European Union exerts its right in exclusive competences without

transferring them to national authorities. The European Union has exclusive competences in such areas as: the customs union; the establishment of the competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market; monetary policy for the Member States whose currency is the euro; the conservation of marine biological resources under the common fisheries policy; common commercial policy; conclusion of international agreements under certain conditions.

Shared competences (CTFEU, art. 4) mean that the European Union and the Member States can legislate and adopt binding acts. The Member States exercise their own competences in areas the European Union does not exercise or has decided not to exercise its own competences. Shared competences apply in the following areas: internal market; social policy, for the aspects defined by the Treaty; economic, social and territorial cohesion; agriculture and fisheries, excluding the conservation of marine biological resources; environment; consumer protection; transport; trans-European networks; energy; area of freedom, security and justice; common safety concerns in public health matters, for the aspects defined by the Treaty; research, technological development, space; development cooperation and humanitarian aid.

Supporting competences (CTFEU, art. 6) are those that the European Union may intervene to support, coordinate or supplement the actions of its Member States. Supporting competences include the following areas: protection and improvement of human health; industry; culture; tourism; education, vocational training, youth and sport; civil protection; administrative cooperation.

In order to draw a demarcation line between competences and crises, it is fair to say that crises happen in the areas in which the Member States have powers, i.e. in those of shared and supporting competences, not in exclusive competences exercised by the European Union. In fact, crises are national crises, not supranational European ones (political, economic, financial, identity, cultural, etc.). Usually crises appear in areas in which the Member States exercise their competences. The motives may have various origin and nature. Challenges for European integration are national(ist) tendencies/interests in imposing improper conduct rules (not values) at EU level. An overcoming approach would be complete fusion between values and interests as the Global Strategy for the European Union's Foreign and Security Policy suggests: "our interests and values go hand in hand [...], our fundamental values are embedded in our interests" (EUGS 2016, 13).

Probably a more correct question would be to ask in another way: who is in crisis? Usually local/national politicians are in crisis or provoke crises for different scopes; local/national tendencies undermining the European Union, European values, European integration, or European unity.

All in all, irrespective of any crisis in which the powers are in local/national areas of competence, it causes the players know each other better, to learn properly weaknesses and strengths, thus working on those weaknesses and exploiting those strengths. The positive side of any crisis is that the European Union gets stronger and more effective in the long run.

United, Effective and Legitimate Entity. Various critical situations occurring in the Member States of the European Union turn to be transferred at supranational level rather attempting to solve them properly at the national level. However, authoritative voices suggest responding in a complex manner to overcome such challenges. In their joint research “Towards a More United and Effective Europe: A Framework for Analysis”, Nathalie Tocci and Giovanni Faleg (2014) evaluate these challenges in terms of unity, effectiveness and governability of the European Union at large. Three questions are under analysis in the vicious cycle of centripetal and centrifugal forces in Europe, i.e. a more united Europe: integration of the core to restore the European Union’s output and input legitimacy; a more effective Europe: heterogeneity within the core and the core-noncore relationship; and squaring the institutional circle: a more governable European Union.

Table 1. Categorisation of Differentiated Integration (adapted from Stubb)

	Multi-speed (time)	Variable geometry (space)	À-la-carte (matter)
Definition	A core of Member States which are able and willing to go further, the underlying assumption being that others will follow	As differences in the integrative structure are unbridgeable, a permanent separation exists between a hard core and less developed integrative units	MS pick and choose, as from a menu, which policy area they would participate in, while subscribing to a minimum set of common objectives
Related model of integration	Multiple speeds	Multiple levels	Multiple clusters
Examples	EMU and pre-in Member States	Schengen agreements	United Kingdom with respect to EMU, Denmark with respect to defence

Source: Apud Tocci and Faleg, 2014.

Revisiting the debates between the core and noncore nature of the Member States, how does integration address the governance of European heterogeneity? Alexander C.-G. Stubb identifies three models of integration: multi-speed, variable geometry and à-la-carte, that correspond to variables of time, space and matter.

The authors identify four non-uniform European integration types: patchwork core, concentric circles, multiple clusters and hub-and-spoke (Tocci and Faleg 2014, 27). They are summarised in the following table.

Table 2. Models of Future EU Governance and Logics of Integration

Model	Logic of Integration
Concentric circles	<i>Variable: geographic space</i> <i>Structure: single core</i> <i>Force: centripetal</i>
Multiple clusters	<i>Variable: matter</i> <i>Structure: multiple cores</i> <i>Force: centripetal</i>
Hub-and-spoke	<i>Variable: space and matter</i> <i>Structure: single core</i> <i>Force: centrifugal</i>
Patchwork core	<i>Variable: space and matter</i> <i>Structure: single heterogeneous core</i> <i>Force: centrifugal or centripetal</i>

Source: Tocci and Faleg, 2014.

It is worth mentioning that these are ideal types and may be applicable in the future. What counts in the table of governance models these are the elements that might be applied in the existing and emerging realities in the larger process of building a united, effective and legitimate European Union.

Conclusions

The European Union is a construction formed by the virtue of law. The founding treaties represent the primary law of the European Union. The law, supranational law, has played a crucial role in the constitution of the European Union. That is European law, the law of the European Union or *acquis communautaire*.

European law has contributed to the EU legal order. In the same time, European law which exceeds the limits of the EU legal order, goes beyond its essential scope. First, European law produces non-legal effects inside the European Union as well. Second, European law produces both legal and non-legal effects outside the European Union by harmonisation.

European law has also produced political, economic, social, and psychological effects inside and outside the European Union. European law has contributed to unification, integration, security and safety. European law contains drivers of values, European values, established in the founding treaties inside and outside the European Union, and drivers of European identity, expressed by structuralist and culturalist models.

European law has contributed to the development of international law and national legal systems of third countries that concluded partnership, cooperation and association agreements with the European Union as a legal approximation has been conferred a central role in developing mutual cooperation.

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